

Table.1 Data information of farmer survey.

		Yield (Mg ha ⁻¹)				N fertilizer (kg N ha ⁻¹)				P fertilizer (kg P ₂ O ₅ ha ⁻¹)				Number of farmer	
		Mean	Median	10 th	90 th	Mean	Median	10 th	90 th	Mean	Median	10 th	90 th		
Cereals	Rice	7.1	7.1	5.9	8.3	176.3	155.0	93.0	288.2	73.5	66.3	42.8	102.8	3498787	
	Wheat	4.2	4.1	2.3	6.0	170.6	153.1	72.2	287.4	85.6	76.0	46.3	139.5	2387235	
	Maize	6.1	5.9	4.5	7.9	200.2	184.4	110.0	314.6	77.8	69.3	37.7	125.1	3159001	
Fruits	Strawberry	17.6	17.0	12.6	22.9	259.0	220.5	80.0	459.6	172.3	139.0	94.0	284.0	3741	
	Orange	17.7	16.8	9.5	22.4	306.9	245.9	142.2	537.2	171.2	140.3	118.1	234.6	10022	
	Citrus	17.2	17.1	12.9	21.6	287.8	235.7	151.7	495.5	151.5	136.6	87.4	237.0	49518	
	Pear	18.8	18.0	14.0	24.8	296.0	229.3	121.7	538.5	162.2	138.2	79.2	262.4	19941	
	Litchi	9.5	8.7	5.8	14.2	293.7	267.1	162.2	411.1	162.8	149.8	115.2	216.2	4174	
	Apple	22.8	22.6	17.5	27.8	380.2	340.3	178.2	666.2	226.9	224.0	114.8	350.2	67940	
	Grape	17.4	16.3	13.5	22.1	300.2	247.0	142.2	542.9	181.7	158.4	94.1	308.9	16553	
	Peach	17.3	17.1	13.0	22.4	279.8	229.3	129.1	478.9	156.7	146.0	88.7	251.1	15434	
	Muskmelon	20.9	19.6	11.7	29.5	231.6	202.9	109.7	360.7	167.3	154.8	74.3	271.2	4873	
	Watermelon	24.1	23.8	22.0	29.5	227.1	198.2	122.4	366.3	139.8	122.5	83.6	210.3	16015	
	Banana	25.3	26.3	23.7	27.8	496.9	462.1	199.1	840.0	225.8	215.4	75.5	358.2	7558	
	Cherry	8.5	7.9	4.6	13.3	294.9	272.9	82.7	461.5	187.7	185.4	34.7	318.5	17727	
	Vegetables	Cabbage	39.4	35.1	16.2	64.5	214.2	211.0	95.6	334.5	83.1	75.0	37.6	131.0	35457
		kidney bean	21.3	18.6	5.6	39.0	224.3	201.2	75.0	352.7	128.1	88.4	25.4	184.5	5706
		Carrot	33.8	34.3	16.3	49.8	190.1	183.0	75.3	297.3	99.9	86.7	40.8	157.1	4920
Cucumber		47.8	42.0	21.9	80.7	304.2	263.8	107.6	572.5	159.0	121.9	71.9	286.6	14801	
Ginger		28.3	24.0	13.6	46.8	298.8	268.8	119.4	567.8	153.5	136.8	89.8	227.6	9591	
Pepper		22.3	19.3	5.5	40.4	229.6	208.5	109.2	375.1	116.0	95.2	68.7	179.5	24831	
Radish		34.2	32.2	17.8	52.7	187.9	171.4	68.1	289.0	81.4	72.1	19.0	134.8	7873	
Eggplant		40.2	37.2	17.2	65.3	302.7	275.9	131.2	484.3	146.5	108.4	76.3	246.0	7117	
Celery		46.7	44.6	20.0	81.9	272.9	244.0	122.8	438.1	129.9	109.1	76.3	204.1	6286	
Garlic		16.4	15.1	6.4	27.3	259.9	255.5	115.4	414.3	112.5	105.0	57.8	181.7	31445	
Tomato		54.9	50.6	31.2	86.1	322.7	285.5	141.9	527.4	177.2	155.3	95.2	301.2	29410	
Soybean		Soybean	2.0	1.9	1.1	3.1	68.2	53.0	26.9	118.0	52.2	47.1	25.0	82.6	478326
Tubbers	Sweet potato	3.8	3.0	0.9	7.9	115.9	111.2	53.5	168.0	68.1	67.9	9.0	111.6	48023	
	Sweet potato (red)	3.9	2.7	0.9	9.2	121.7	117.0	52.9	176.1	72.3	68.8	5.3	120.3	13807	
	Potato	4.2	3.2	1.7	8.4	168.0	163.8	88.7	231.1	112.3	103.8	60.7	175.5	136872	
	Cassava	4.1	3.1	1.7	7.4	150.4	156.8	88.6	194.0	87.3	87.4	63.8	142.9	5100	
Peanut	Peanut	3.0	2.8	1.6	4.6	108.8	102.0	71.3	143.2	78.7	70.2	50.1	127.8	200282	
Rapeseed	Rapeseed	2.0	1.9	1.0	2.9	130.5	136.7	56.3	192.6	65.1	62.4	34.5	99.3	294511	
Sugarcane	Sugarcane	50.4	48.5	20.4	84.4	379.0	433.5	242.9	441.1	191.1	213.5	89.9	282.3	46695	
Others	Chinese chestnut	4.6	3.3	1.0	10.4	185.1	151.5	66.2	329.8	97.2	93.7	45.3	179.7	5719	
	Faba bean	2.4	1.9	0.7	4.6	77.8	52.9	0.0	166.1	67.4	57.3	17.9	98.9	9612	
	Tea	2.1	1.2	0.3	5.6	245.6	211.8	117.9	411.3	93.1	78.1	0.9	149.0	46095	
	Barley	3.7	3.0	1.1	6.6	154.3	148.9	56.4	238.2	78.8	77.3	43.2	116.6	43328	
	Sorghum	3.9	3.5	1.1	6.9	145.4	124.1	55.6	244.9	79.6	75.1	0.0	122.7	5276	
	Millet	2.7	2.2	0.9	4.8	122.2	108.6	36.3	213.7	64.9	59.9	4.9	101.9	22740	
	Flaxseed	1.3	1.0	0.4	2.4	98.2	86.7	26.7	176.6	67.7	64.2	59.9	96.8	20704	
	Mung bean	1.4	1.0	0.4	2.6	91.2	61.5	19.1	192.5	61.2	49.7	0.0	98.1	12578	
	Buckwheat	1.3	1.0	0.4	2.4	76.4	58.2	0.0	163.0	51.5	43.2	0.0	80.0	8952	
	Highland barley	2.5	2.1	1.1	4.0	84.0	70.4	2.7	142.0	58.6	52.0	0.3	92.1	18920	
	Mulberry	19.1	14.8	3.2	37.9	336.4	301.8	197.8	583.1	108.5	93.4	30.7	181.9	13075	
	Sugar beet	35.1	30.1	10.5	62.7	202.6	204.0	100.3	323.4	128.8	133.6	133.7	176.2	9838	
	Pea	2.6	1.6	0.6	6.6	82.4	59.3	0.0	176.6	56.9	53.0	0.0	92.2	7667	
	Sunflower	2.2	1.9	0.8	3.7	154.6	137.5	69.8	239.9	87.2	92.0	67.0	120.1	53916	
	Tobacco	2.1	1.6	1.0	3.4	155.6	134.5	97.1	247.1	119.0	119.1	140.5	151.0	44546	
Hulless oat	1.6	1.1	0.4	2.7	63.5	41.1	15.4	126.2	52.1	48.7	5.2	78.6	19867		
Jujube	12.4	9.8	1.9	26.2	280.1	222.6	123.6	491.7	195.7	159.7	98.3	330.1	9597		
Sesame	1.2	0.9	0.3	2.4	98.9	78.7	45.0	163.3	49.3	43.3	0.0	80.0	14290		
Ramie	2.0	1.6	0.5	3.7	199.6	210.1	123.4	304.8	67.0	60.1	91.3	88.1	6416		

Table.2 Data information of top 10% producers.

		Yield (Mg ha ⁻¹)				N fertilizer (kg N ha ⁻¹)				P fertilizer (kg P ₂ O ₅ ha ⁻¹)				Number of farmer	
		Mean	Median	10 th	90 th	Mean	Median	10 th	90 th	Mean	Median	10 th	90 th		
Cereals	Rice	8.3	8.3	7.2	9.5	155.7	156.0	102.7	215.0	70.5	71.3	40.8	94.0	348721	
	Wheat	5.2	5.2	2.9	7.1	153.9	154.1	83.3	219.5	90.3	90.4	47.0	132.2	233865	
	Maize	7.7	7.3	5.7	9.9	172.6	172.6	99.7	242.7	81.1	81.2	42.7	113.8	314188	
	Strawberry	20.7	18.8	14.0	28.8	215.2	210.4	104.6	290.4	164.8	151.4	122.5	184.9	377	
	Orange	22.3	21.4	13.3	28.8	253.9	246.9	167.8	315.5	167.7	176.8	113.9	179.9	971	
	Citrus	24.3	23.6	16.6	29.7	242.3	225.6	167.6	321.9	155.5	158.3	97.6	179.6	5188	
	Pear	23.9	23.4	18.3	32.4	254.5	221.8	117.0	357.3	159.9	151.7	62.1	206.5	2139	
Fruits	Litchi	15.0	12.4	6.7	22.9	273.7	269.8	171.9	340.8	196.0	168.9	125.6	220.6	355	
	Apple	30.1	29.1	24.8	36.0	333.4	351.7	202.2	413.4	227.8	247.3	122.1	269.2	6992	
	Grape	22.0	21.3	16.6	28.8	249.7	233.3	164.9	338.1	173.9	164.9	111.9	234.7	1824	
	Peach	22.5	21.6	16.5	29.0	229.3	210.4	124.1	297.0	152.2	151.1	108.7	177.7	1652	
	Muskmelon	24.2	23.4	12.4	33.4	197.9	202.0	119.3	220.3	158.2	154.3	97.6	197.9	505	
	Watermelon	29.8	28.4	27.2	36.0	186.4	188.0	146.6	220.4	133.1	131.2	97.6	152.5	1893	
	Banana	30.8	30.9	33.1	35.9	431.0	493.9	210.9	479.9	221.4	225.2	78.6	304.3	718	
	Cherry	12.6	12.0	5.7	17.0	234.8	238.5	99.4	275.0	185.9	210.6	39.0	232.5	1756	
		Cabbage	48.2	45.3	25.4	75.3	197.2	210.3	120.3	228.5	96.8	108.7	0.0	116.9	3922
		kidney bean	27.0	20.4	8.6	50.1	214.2	214.9	101.6	242.8	152.3	120.1	27.8	168.9	572
	Carrot	38.0	34.5	19.6	54.1	170.8	166.0	94.1	198.0	116.3	117.9	59.6	145.1	504	
	Cucumber	57.0	48.5	29.4	100.3	269.4	249.8	133.7	368.6	176.7	165.8	95.4	234.4	1681	
Vegetables	Ginger	33.1	28.9	15.7	50.1	271.8	284.6	142.5	344.3	179.7	198.9	120.4	216.0	967	
	Pepper	28.9	25.9	7.5	46.1	212.6	213.5	130.7	260.0	138.1	138.2	91.4	158.1	2811	
	Radish	39.4	38.1	19.6	54.4	167.7	171.6	74.2	201.1	91.9	96.8	0.0	117.0	947	
	Eggplant	45.7	40.7	19.6	72.3	279.8	266.7	199.7	342.6	173.7	147.4	110.5	234.0	853	
	Celery	52.7	50.0	25.9	80.2	241.7	237.2	160.4	283.3	134.9	147.4	79.5	143.7	705	
	Garlic	19.5	17.0	7.3	30.1	237.3	253.0	166.8	262.7	133.0	147.4	85.0	147.1	3274	
	Tomato	63.8	56.6	39.2	97.6	287.3	284.4	193.9	347.0	202.6	209.6	119.2	246.0	3206	
	Soybean	Soybean	3.8	3.8	2.4	4.2	84.9	85.4	38.9	100.6	63.9	64.2	39.0	71.9	48426
		Sweet potato	5.4	5.6	2.6	7.4	99.6	101.7	29.6	134.2	67.0	69.3	0.0	87.0	5141
Tubbers	Sweet potato (red)	5.5	5.6	2.5	8.2	104.6	110.5	37.4	145.9	69.2	71.2	0.0	90.3	1462	
	Potato	5.7	5.6	4.6	7.3	146.6	146.5	79.7	180.3	110.0	115.5	88.2	137.3	14366	
	Cassava	6.3	6.2	5.2	7.7	152.3	147.3	111.7	199.6	101.4	94.3	91.8	123.4	464	
Peanut	Peanut	4.6	4.6	3.4	5.4	100.4	100.5	61.5	112.8	73.5	73.5	46.0	88.4	20841	
Rapeseed	Rapeseed	3.2	3.2	2.3	3.6	123.3	123.7	80.3	160.0	63.8	64.6	40.5	80.0	30568	
Sugarcane	Sugarcane	82.0	81.8	81.8	84.5	341.2	340.7	333.5	340.7	183.8	183.6	166.2	183.6	4804	
	Chinese chestnut	5.7	5.2	1.6	7.3	190.4	171.5	58.8	294.8	106.9	108.8	0.0	173.1	559	
	Faba bean	2.9	2.5	1.1	3.8	82.7	68.6	0.0	153.1	74.2	72.0	0.0	93.4	1008	
	Tea	3.0	2.1	0.5	5.1	259.4	252.9	148.1	386.4	94.4	93.2	0.0	146.0	4806	
	Barley	4.1	4.3	2.2	4.2	165.5	186.3	76.2	225.9	89.8	95.3	109.5	112.1	4483	
	Sorghum	4.3	4.8	1.7	4.6	156.9	153.5	74.2	222.2	89.6	95.3	0.0	134.4	531	
	Millet	3.5	3.5	1.6	3.6	132.0	138.1	34.9	207.0	77.0	78.7	0.0	115.3	2351	
	Flaxseed	1.9	1.7	0.9	2.1	111.1	112.6	35.5	174.5	77.0	84.9	73.4	98.7	2083	
	Mung bean	1.7	1.5	0.9	1.9	98.4	80.9	28.1	163.8	70.7	60.5	0.0	105.8	1271	
	Buckwheat	1.6	1.7	0.6	1.8	78.4	67.1	0.0	146.9	60.9	55.0	0.0	79.9	895	
Others	Highland barley	3.0	3.2	1.8	3.0	91.0	88.2	4.6	126.4	67.9	67.1	0.0	93.1	1884	
	Mulberry	24.6	24.4	5.4	30.8	364.3	380.7	195.6	495.4	126.7	131.9	0.0	186.8	1345	
	Sugar beet	39.8	44.6	16.2	41.9	210.4	239.3	127.3	293.2	150.8	153.1	189.7	200.9	866	
	Pea	3.2	2.3	1.1	5.7	93.0	73.1	0.0	175.1	66.6	62.1	0.0	93.5	824	
	Sunflower	2.8	2.9	1.6	3.0	165.9	173.4	98.4	221.4	103.6	111.7	112.0	129.8	5537	
	Tobacco	2.5	2.4	1.6	2.6	161.7	162.5	119.4	215.9	127.6	141.2	179.2	152.2	4648	
	Hullless oat	2.0	1.8	0.9	2.0	70.1	55.5	27.3	125.7	64.0	62.7	0.0	80.7	1979	
	Jujube	14.6	12.6	3.9	21.6	288.1	265.4	115.0	459.7	217.8	189.6	98.9	373.5	985	
	Sesame	1.6	1.3	0.6	2.2	111.1	108.5	55.1	155.0	54.1	57.1	0.0	78.2	1486	
	Ramie	2.6	2.6	1.3	2.9	213.3	263.6	156.1	262.5	83.5	82.9	134.0	89.0	573	